

Static hydrodynamic cavitation as external gas-liquid transfer system for biological biogas upgrading

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Abstract

The study deals with the use of a static hydrodynamic cavitation device as a gas-to-liquid mass transfer system to provide the biological conversion of carbon dioxide into methane in a dedicated bioreactor. An orifice plate hydrodynamic cavitation device was coupled with a thermophilic pilot-scale bioreactor inoculated with a mixed inoculum sampled from a centralized full-scale anaerobic digester treating sewage sludge. The bioreactor was fed with hydrogen and carbon dioxide and then, with a mix of hydrogen and biogas, and monitored in terms of process efficiency and stability. Gas sparging through the static hydrodynamic cavitation device was feasible under the operating conditions applied, allowing to achieve a methane concentration above 96% in the gas produced and a hydrogen solubilization efficiency of about 100% without compromising biological stability. However, during the biogas upgrading experimental stage a significant foam formation was observed in the reactor headspace, which led to a lower bioavailability of the CO₂ and increased complexities in process management.

Keywords

Biological biogas upgrading; hydrodynamic cavitation; hydrogenotrophic archaea; biomethane

INTRODUCTION

Biological hydrogenotrophic methanation (BHM) of carbon dioxide (CO₂) through methanogenic archaea offers a potential alternative to traditional biogas upgrading methods based on chemical-physical removal of CO₂ (e.g. pressure swing adsorption, membrane separation, water scrubbing, etc.), due to its higher potential biomethane productivity, flexibility in treating different raw biogas quality, and capability to enable the integration of various renewable energy production infrastructures according to power to biomethane concept (Bellini et al., 2022). Although biogas upgrading based on BHM process has been successfully implemented at a demonstration scale, its widespread adoption is limited by high investment and operating costs (Chatzis et al., 2024). Therefore, finding technical solutions to improve process efficiency and return on investment is a challenge for research efforts. A critical limitation of BHM is represented by the low solubility of H₂ in liquid media, limiting the microbial uptake of exogenous H₂ and its conversion into CH₄. Conventional approaches for efficient hydrogen (H₂) solubilization and dispersion in liquid media include high-speed mixing, gas diffusers, membrane reactors (Jensen et al., 2021). Hydrodynamic cavitation (HC) has emerged as a novel approach to promote gas-liquid mass transfer, by exploiting micro/nano bubble formation via static (*i.e.* venturi tubes) or dynamic devices (*i.e.* rotative system) (Giuliano et al., 2023). The present study deals with the use of a static HC system as an external gas solubilization system in the ex-situ biological biogas upgrading process. The static HC system consists of an orifice plate (sHC-OP), which has been successfully applied in wastewater treatment to provide energy-efficient small bubble generation and chemical dosing (Panda et al., 2020), although it poses challenges as to avoid cell damage in the biological conversion processes when installed in a closed-loop circuit with suspended microbial biomass.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The experimental trials were conducted in a thermophilic pilot-scale bioreactor (V_{tot}=194L) filled with 177L of diluted anaerobic sludge sampled from a centralized full-scale AD plant treating municipal sewage sludge. The reactor's slurry was continuously recirculated with a screw-pump and acted as carrier fluid for the dissolved gas. The sHC-OP device consisted of a stainless-steel modified

orifice plate swirling jet device (Mancuso et al., 2016). It was positioned at the bottom of the bioreactor as an external unit, along the internal recirculation line of the liquid slurry, which also housed the probes for real-time monitoring (pH, dissolved CO₂ and ORP). The exogenous H₂ gas flow was provided by three electrolyzers (CINEL, Italy), while pure CO₂ and the synthetic biogas mixture (CH₄/CO₂ 55:45 v/v) were injected from separate cylinders (Sapio, Italy). The output gas was continuously collected from the reactor's headspace and monitored in terms of quantity and quality. The slurry was sampled on weekly basis to monitor the main process stability parameters (pH, total and partial alkalinity, volatile fatty acids). The whole experiment lasted about 100 days, and it was divided into two major stages according to the inlet gas composition (Table 1): the start-up phase with H₂ and CO₂ injection (S1) and the ex-situ biogas upgrading with H₂, CO₂ and CH₄ injection (S2). During both experimental stages, the volumetric ratio between H₂ and CO₂ was maintained at 4:1. Reference parameters for evaluating the performance of biological methanation of external gaseous substrates consist in the CH₄ production rate (MPR), the gas retention time (GRT), the solubilization efficiency of the reactant gas, with reference to H₂ (η_{H_2}) and CO₂ (η_{CO_2}), and their conversion efficiency into CH₄ (Y_{H_2} and Y_{CO_2}). All the performance and chemical parameters were calculated in accordance with our previous study (Giuliano et al., 2023). Genomic DNA was extracted using DNeasy PowerSoil Pro Kits (Quiagen). Full-length 16S sequencing of bacteria and archaea has been performed using SQK-16S114.24 and SQK-NBD114.24 Oxford Nanopore kits, respectively.

Table 1. Experimental conditions adopted in the pilot plant

Parameter (Unit)	Stage 1 (S1)	Stage 2 (S2)
Total reactor volume (L) [V_{tot}]	194	194
Working volume (L) [V_w]	177	177
Inlet gas composition (% v/v)	H ₂ (80%) + CO ₂ (20%)	H ₂ + Biogas (CO ₂ 45-50%; CH ₄ :50-55%)
H ₂ /CO ₂ ratio (v/v)	80:20	80:20
Internal pressure (bar) [P_{hs}]	2	2
Temperature (°C) [T]	55	55
Gas loading rate (L_{gas}/L_rh) [GLR]	0.03-0.33	0.2-0.4
Internal liquid recirculation flowrate (L/h) [Q_r]	1200	1200

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

During the start-up phase (S1), the GLR was progressively increased up to 7.75 L_{gas}/L_{rd} and kept constant for 2 weeks (weeks 7-8), during which the trends of the main biological parameters (VFA, total and partial alkalinity) showed substantial stability (Figure 1a). In particular, after 3 weeks the average VFA concentration dropped from 416.5 ± 85.6 mg/L to 141.0 ± 69.1 mg/L and remained constant despite the GLR variation. Likewise, dCO₂ undergoes an evident reduction after 3 weeks reaching an average value on weekly basis of 1.3 ± 0.2 mmol/L at the end of S1 stage. The rapid and concomitant increase of CO₂ consumption matched up with both the increase in pH (from 7.6 ± 0.02 to 8.26 ± 0.05) and a decrease of ORP (from -448.8 ± 17.7 mV to -530 ± 5.6 mV) (data not shown) suggesting a successful adaptation of the hydrogenotrophic microbial biomass in the reactor (Wagner et al., 2018). This was confirmed by the observed composition of the gas leaving the bioreactor and the conversion efficiencies of gaseous substrates into CH₄. Indeed, at the beginning of the feeding operation, a continuous increase in CH₄ content was observed recording values higher than 90% after

two weeks (Figure 1b). Moreover, the employment of the sHC-OP device as gas-to-liquid transfer system resulted in high solubilization efficiencies of both H₂ and CO₂ (more than 98% and 96% respectively) during the S1. The temporal profiles of the conversion efficiencies Y_{H2} and Y_{CO2} (Figure 1b), show that at the end of S1 the predominant metabolism seems to be the one catalyzed by hydrogenotrophic microorganisms, as the values tend towards the maximum theoretical value given by the Sabatier's reaction ($4\text{H}_2 + \text{CO}_2 \rightarrow \text{CH}_4 + 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$), reaching an average value of $0.22 \pm 0.1 \text{ LCH}_4/\text{LH}_{2\text{in}}$ and $0.95 \pm 0.07 \text{ LCH}_4/\text{LCO}_{2\text{in}}$ respectively (week 8). At the beginning of S2 stage (week 9), the feeding ratio between H₂ and CO₂ was kept unchanged, maintaining the same CO₂ and H₂ loading rates of the last part of S1 (weeks 7-8). Consequently, considering the increase of the total input gas flow rate (H₂ + Biogas), the GRT decreased to about 3 hours. Under these operating conditions, foaming formation in the reactor headspace was observed, leading to a general worsening in process performance. The reactor performance decrease may have been caused by the coupling of GRT reduction and the dilution effect due to the presence of CH₄ in the input gas, resulting in a lower contact time between the gaseous substrates (H₂ and CO₂) and the microorganisms (Rittmann, 2015). Furthermore, a second foaming event was observed at the end of S2 (weeks 13-14) with a consequent worsening in process performance, when similar hydraulic operating conditions (ratio between inlet gas flow rate and internal liquid recirculation flow rate), suggesting a failure in the functioning of the gas-liquid transfer system (Ozonek, 2012). To avoid damage to the measuring equipment, a reduction of the GLR was applied during weeks 10-11. This strategy resulted in a temporary improvement of the gas quality in terms of CH₄ and H₂ content. However, from week 11 onwards, an increase in VFA concentration (up to 552 mg/L, mostly acetic acid) was recorded, indicating a simultaneous stimulation of homoacetogenesis route ($4\text{H}_2 + 2\text{CO}_2 \rightarrow \text{CH}_3\text{COOH} + 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$). Furthermore, the increase of Y_{H2} occurred at the end of S2 suggested an additional acetoclastic methanogenesis pathway ($\text{CH}_3\text{COOH} \rightarrow \text{CH}_4 + 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$) (Paillet et al., 2025; Tsapekos et al., 2022). Sequencing revealed the community shifted from a Nitrososphaeraceae-dominated inoculum to one enriched in Methanobacteriaceae which convert CO₂ and H₂ into methane (Nakamura et al, 2013). During S2 phase the relative abundance of Nitrososphaeraceae rose again, coinciding with process inefficiency. Genomic analysis of bacterial community showed an increase with relative abundance of Tissierellia in S2, which has been associated with the increase of acetic acid in alkaline conditions (Jiménez-Páez et al, 2023) and has been shown to grow using only H₂ and CO₂ as substrates. The increase in relative abundance of this species could be linked to the general worsening of methanation efficiency, while keeping low levels of dissolved CO₂ and a slight increase in acetic acid content (Zaybak et al, 2013). The achievement of a high H₂ solubilization efficiency, except for periods in which foam production was observed, suggests an effective operation of the sHC-OP as a gas-liquid transfer system under the operating conditions tested. Further experiments are needed to effectively control the foam formation by modifying the operational parameters of the HC system.

Figure 1. a) Time profile of the main biological stability parameters (VFA=volatile fatty acids; TA=total alkalinity; PA=partial Alkalinity; dCO₂=dissolved CO₂); Weeks of sampling for DNA extraction are indicated with a dot on the graph b) Outlet gas composition (v/v %) and substrate

conversion efficiency (Y_{H_2} and Y_{CO_2} , % over maximum theoretic efficiency according to Sabatier's Reaction).

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